

Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids. Part VI. Further Investigation of the Viscosity Variations during Coagulation.

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In Part V of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 329) results were given for the changes of viscosity during the *slow* coagulations of colloid arsenious sulphide (both pure and also when protected by different amounts of gelatine) produced by differently concentrated solutions of potassium chloride. It was observed that (a) immediately after the commencement of the coagulation the viscosity almost always showed a *diminution* in the range, 0.7 to 1.8 % of the initial viscosity, and that (b) the viscosity—time curves showed a number of well marked maxima and minima which were attributed to the coagulation process (at any rate in the *slow* region) consisting of a succession of changes, both as to the size and nature of the coagulating particles (*vide infra*). In view of the fact that both these findings invalidate the use of viscosity as a *general*, qualitative measure of the degree of coagulation at least in the *slow* region, and especially since the initial fall in viscosity mentioned in (a) does not appear to have been studied previously in the literature, it was considered desirable to investigate (a) and (b) in more detail. To this end, in the following experiments coagulations of the arsenious sulphide sol have been studied in which differently concentrated solutions of AlCl_3 , $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$, ThCl_4 , KF , KCl , KBr , and KI were used as coagulants, the sol being also varied over a suitable range in each case.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The general experimental procedure was mostly similar to that described in Part V (*loc. cit.*). The temperature of the thermostat was maintained at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in all the experiments. The colloid content of the sol was determined by the Kessler's method (*cf.* Part I, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 11). 20 C. c. of the sol

were kept in the Scarpa tube (called P in Fig. A, Part V) immersed in the thermostat. To this was added an equal volume of the coagulator solution whose concentration was varied by mixing appropriate volumes of water of the standard solution of the electrolyte chosen. Both these were allowed to attain the thermostat temperature before mixing in the Scarpa tube. Immediately after this, the mixture was given a rotatory motion twice and the corresponding mean time noted. The viscosity of the coagulating sol was then determined by Scarpa's method with modifications described in Part V. By preliminary experiments the concentrations of the electrolyte solution and of the sol were so chosen, that the coagulating sol did not flocculate, that is, show heterogeneities of even fine visible precipitate tending to leave a deposit on the walls of the viscometer in at least 5 hours.

It has been noted previously (*loc. cit.*) that the initial fall of viscosity occurs so soon after the start of coagulation that precautions are necessary to measure it fully and accurately. Some improvement over the previously adopted procedure was made in these experiments (for details compare a forthcoming paper by Joshi and Joga Rao on the viscosity variations due to molecular chemical changes) by dispensing with the letting out of water from the aspirator A_1 into the beaker B (*cf.* Fig. A, Part V) in order to establish negative pressure in the Scarpa tube before each observation of the time of rise of the liquid. Following this rise, the water level in the manometer limb connected with the tube P is slightly depressed. This is easily adjusted to the original value by simply adding a small quantity of water to that in the beaker B. This results in a considerable saving of time, and what is more, is particularly suited for measurements during the initial stages of the coagulation. The suction used in these experiments was 26 cm. of water.

Curves 1-4, in Fig. 1 show the influence of varying the sol concentration in the range 1.5 to 0.188 g. As_2S_3 per litre, the concentration of the coagulant being kept constant at $N/40,000$. Curves 5-6 refer to coagulations of sols of a fixed colloid content (1.5 g. As_2S_3 per litre) and the coagulant concentrations varied in the range $N/20,000$ to $N/27,000$. Figs. 2 and 3 refer to similar experiments with thorium nitrate and thorium chloride solutions. Results of the use of solutions of the various potassium halide solutions are given in Figs. 4 and 5. The data recorded in Tables

I—V were obtained from curves in the corresponding figures. The colloid and the electrolyte concentrations given in the third and fourth vertical columns in these tables refer to their values in the coagulating mixture.

TABLE I (cf. Fig. 1).

Sol = 20 c.c.

Composi- tion of the mixture.		Colloid conc. As_2S_3 g./litre.	Electrolyte conc.	Initial vis- cosity in centipoise.	First mini- mum visco- sity in C.P. η_M .	Percentage diminution of visco- sity.	Time corres- ponding to η_M in mins.
Water.	N/1000 $AlCl_3$.						
19 c.c.	1 c.c.	1.5	N/40000	0.728	—	—	—
"	"	0.75	"	0.734	0.729	0.64	25
"	"	0.375	"	0.733	0.728	0.64	25
"	"	0.188	"	0.735	"	"	25
18.5	1.5	1.5	N/26270	0.735	0.732	0.39	27
18.35	1.65	"	N/24250	0.727	0.723	0.52	21
18.15	1.75	"	N/22860	0.731	0.727	0.46	27
18.75	1.85	"	N/21620	0.751	0.739	0.3	19
18	2	"	N/20000	0.742	0.740	0.23	19

TABLE II (cf. Fig. 2).

Sol = 20 c.c.

Water.		N/500- $Th(NO_3)_4$.					
19	1	1.5	N/120000	0.735	0.733	0.30	25
"	"	0.75	"	0.729	0.727	0.27	—
"	"	0.188	"	0.728	0.727	0.18	13
"	"	0.094	"	0.727	0.726	0.14	27

TABLE III (cf. Fig. 3).

Sol = 20 c.c.

Water.		N/500. $Th(Cl)_4$.					
18.6	1.4 c.c.	1.5	N/14290	0.736	0.734	0.20	38
18.5	1.5	"	N/13500	0.725	—	—	—
18	2	"	N/10000	0.741	0.738	0.48	25
17.7	2.3	"	N/8500	0.730	0.724	0.70	39
17	3	"	N/6500	0.738	0.737	—	—

TABLE IV (cf. FIG. 4).

Sol = 20 c.c.

Composi- tion of the mixture.	Colloid conc. of the As_2S_3 g./litre.	Electrolyte conc.	Initial vis- cosity in centipoise	First mini- mum visco- sity in C.P. η_M .	Percentage diminution of visco- sity.	Time corres- ponding to η_M in mins.
Water. N/10- KF.						
18 c.c. 2 c.c.	1.5	N/200	0.781	0.721	1.3	60
16 4	..	N/100	0.738	0.727	1.5	25
18 2	0.75	N/200	0.730	0.723	1.1	37
16 4	..	N/100	0.732	0.723	1.17	75
N/10- KCl.						
18 2 c.c.	1.5	N/200	0.729	0.724	0.73	37
16 4	..	N/100	0.732	0.723	1.2	25
.. 4	0.75	N/100	0.724	0.722	0.36	25
18 2	..	N/200	0.731	0.720	1.42	50

TABLE V (cf. FIG. 5).

N/10- KBr.						
16 c.c. 4 c.c.	1.5	N/100	0.729	0.722	0.85	38
18 2	..	N/200	0.734	0.727	0.98	38
18 2	0.75	N/200	0.729	0.722	0.85	50
N/10- KI.						
16 4 c.c.	1.5	N/100	0.727	0.720	0.98	25
4	0.75	..	0.728	0.725	0.41	25

DISCUSSION.

Amongst the numerous methods used in order to follow the progress of coagulation, the earliest and widest used depend upon the variation, of the intensity of light scattered by, and of the relative transparency of the coagulating sol (Mukherjee and coworkers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 350, 1563; 1924, 125, 794; Lottermoser, *Kolloid Z.*, 1914, 15, 145; Desai, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, 24, 181). Hatschek's colorimetric method (cf. Anderson, *ibid.*, 1924, 19, 626) and that using the ultramicroscope are more accurate and their

results (especially of the last) simpler to interpret, but are restricted in the range of their applicability. A considerable mass of data has also resulted from the use by different workers of chemical methods of measuring coagulation (Paine, *Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1912, 4, 24; Paine and Evans, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1924, 24, 649; Freundlich and Basu, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 115, 203; Joshi and Prabhu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 11, 337). Joshi and Lal (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 61) have measured coagulation by a new method, *viz.*, by the determination of the surface tension. Reference also must be made here of the results of numerous workers (for a review, *cf.* Part V) on viscosity measurements although restricted, in by far the majority of cases, to a determination of the significant transpiration times only. An outstanding indication of these results is that in general the progress of coagulation is continuous with the coagulation time. It is of considerable interest, therefore, to point out that the confirmation by the results recorded in this paper, of the previous observation (*cf.* Part V) of (a) the initial fall of viscosity, and of (b) the marked discontinuities on the viscosity-time curves affords a definite evidence of the limitation of the above deduction at least in the *slow* region of coagulation. These results (and those reported in Part V) also show the superiority of our viscosity method in revealing features of the coagulation process, which otherwise practically escape detection (*cf.* Joshi and Joga Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 247).

An examination of the foregoing results also shows (Figs. 1—5) that the magnitude of the initial fall, and the subsequent fluctuations of viscosity are affected considerably by the values of the concentration both of the colloid and the electrolyte. It is also seen (*cf.* curves 1—4, Fig. 1) that the initial fall in viscosity tends to diminish both for the smallest and largest concentrations of the sol, and of the coagulator. It is well known that the rate of coagulation increases rapidly as the coagulator concentration is raised, and ordinarily, the viscosity would rise rapidly in such coagulations. It is to be anticipated, therefore, that in these cases, the initial fall in the viscosity would be to some extent masked by the viscosity rise due to the rapidity of coagulation. It must be stressed, however, that the above deductions represent only a tentative conclusion, not quite free from exceptions (*cf.* Figs. 2—3), and a far more detailed investigation would be necessary to obtain a complete correlation of the progress of viscosity as a function of the two concentration

FIG. 1.
Coagulation by AlCl_3 .

Curves 1—4 refer to $N/40,000 \text{ AlCl}_3 + 1.5 \text{ g.}, 0.75 \text{ g.}, 0.375 \text{ g.},$ and $0.188 \text{ g. As}_2\text{S}_3$ per litre respectively. Curves 5—9 refer to $N/26270, N/24250, N/22680, N/2162$ and $N/20,000 \text{ AlCl}_3$ respectively $+ 1.5 \text{ g. As}_2\text{S}_3$ per litre.

FIG. 2.

Coagulation by $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$.

Curves 1—4 refer to $N/20,000 \text{ Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 + 1.5 \text{ g.}, 0.75 \text{ g.}, 0.188 \text{ g.},$ and 0.04 g. of As_2S_3 per litre respectively.

factors in the *slow* region. For example, curve, 1 (Fig. 3), curves 1—2 (Fig. 4), and curve 3 (Fig. 5) show that a coagulation is not necessarily accompanied by a net rise of viscosity. Results fully confirming this possibility under appropriate conditions have been obtained recently in these laboratories and will be published shortly.

It was also observed in Part V (*loc. cit.*) that subsequent to the initial fall and prior to its eventual rise, in a number of coagulations, the viscosity increased markedly slowly, indicative of *autocatalysis*. This is detectable in curves 5, 6, 7 (Fig. 1). It is well known that a small percentage change in the coagulator concentration affects the coagulation time by several times in the *slow* region. It is

FIG. 3.

Coagulation by ThCl_4 .

Curves 1—5 refer to $N/14290$, $N/13500$, $N/10,000$, $N/8500$ and $N/6500$ ThCl_4 respectively and 1.5 g. As_2S_3 per litre.

interesting, therefore, to notice that the time corresponding to the attainment of the first minimum on the viscosity-time curves varies irregularly in the range 20—60 minutes although the nature and the strength of the coagulator and also of the colloid were varied over a wide range (*cf.* Tables I-V). Results obtained previously were similar to this (*loc. cit.*). It might also be added that the value of the initial fall expressed as a percentage observed previously for potassium chloride solutions is similar to that observed now for solutions of KF , KBr , and KI .

FIG. 4.
Coagulation by KF and KCl.

FIG. 5.
Coagulation by KBr and KI.

Curve 1- N/100 KBr + 1.5g. As_2S_3 per litre.

2- N/200 " " " "

3- " " 0.75g. " "

4- N/100 KI + 1.5g. " "

5- " " 0.75g. " "

SUMMARY.

Results are given for the variation of viscosity when differently concentrated sols of arsenious sulphide were coagulated in the slow region, by solutions of KCl, KBr, KI, KF, AlCl₃, ThCl₄, and Th(NO₃)₄. Usually, though not invariably, viscosity first diminishes to a well marked minimum and then rises in a number of breaks. The first tends to diminish when the concentration of the sol and of the coagulator is either too high or too low. Both the above features disappear during rapid coagulations.

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